

A MASS SPECTROMETRIC STUDY OF THE CONSTITUENT

INTERFACE INTERACTION IN METAL-POLYMER COMPOSITES

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A study of polymer interaction with a metal surface is carried out in connection with the problems of producing composite materials and of investigating the nature of adhesion of solids (1). Adhesion is the result of adsorption as the primary event of polymer interaction with metal surface. In addition, thermal and thermal oxidation processes at the interface also play frequently an important role in the formation of a polymer-to-metal adhesion bond. A study of the thermal destruction of ultra-thin polymer films adsorbed on metal surface can provide information on the interaction of a polymer and metal at the interface and, hence, on the actual mechanism of adhesion.

The report deals with results of a study of the thermal degradation of some ultra-thin polymers films by the flash pyrolysis technique combined with a time-of-flight mass spectrometer (2). The dependence of the thermal degradation activation energy E of polymer films on their average thickness (i.e. the surface concentration of macromolecules) \bar{H} was measured in the range of a few hundreds to a few \AA (fig). The values of E for films of polymers with close bulk parameters of thermal degradation were compared. As shown by these data, polymers containing specific functional groups, e.g. carboxyls, are characterized by high strength of adhesion with a metal (e.g. polymethylmetacrylate) and reduce substantially the activation energy of thermal degradation when used in

Dependence of the thermal degradation activation energy of polymer films on their average thickness: • -polystyrene, ○ -polymethylmetacrylate.

the form of ultrathin films. Polymers of the opposite type (e.g. polystyrene) reveal independence of the activation energy of thermal degradation on \bar{H} (3).

The decrease of E for ultrathin films of polymer like polymethylmetacrylate may be explained as due to rearrangement of the electronic structure of adsorbed macromolecules on active centers of the substrate producing of bonds in the macromolecules. The results obtained support and explain the well-known transition through a maximum in the dependence of adhesion strength in the polymer-metal systems on the intensity of activation of the surfaces to be coupled. The molecular adhesion of polymer to metal can thus be provided only by adequate cohesion strength of the macromolecules.

At less than monolayer concentrations of macromolecules (i.e. with isolated macromolecules) on the substrate a specific feature of secondary radical reactions in thermal destruction was revealed which is associated with a transfer from the mechanism of bulk polymer degradation to the fracture of isolated macromolecules.

On the whole, the use of mass spectrometry in this case permits to obtain information on the parameters and structure

of the transition zone in the metal-polymer composites, on the interaction of constituents at the interface and the nature of active adsorption centers and of the catalysis of macromolecules.

References

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